

Research Topic

“The Cross-cultural Consumers’ Attitudes towards Sustainability of Product in the Textile Industry”

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Abstract

This research aimed to explore consumer attitudes towards recycled clothing among diverse cultural backgrounds, focusing on how cultural values influence sustainable fashion choices. The objectives of the study were to identify key concerns and preferences for sustainable initiatives from textile companies, examine the impact of cultural influences on purchasing behaviors, and analyze the usage patterns and primary drivers behind consumer decisions related to sustainable textiles. To achieve these objectives, a qualitative research methodology was employed, involving semi-structured interviews with 50 participants representing various cultural backgrounds in the UK. The data collection process ensured diverse perspectives were captured, allowing for an in-depth exploration of participants' thoughts and feelings regarding sustainable fashion. The interview data was transcribed to a word document and names were given to each of them before going through thematic coding in which the research first formulating the initial codes, which was done through open coding where the research refined these codes through axial coding to identify connections between one coding which was followed by selective coding in order to make more improvements and focus on the central themes of the study. The findings showed major trends for the wastage of environment, society, and culture that helped the consumers to decide on recycled clothing. Based on the research findings, customer concern was towards products' sustainability, fair employment and transparent sourcing with cultural values highly influencing the choice of sustainable clothing. The following recommendations were made depending on the result for textile firms, policy makers and consumers. For textile companies, it is essential to align product offerings with consumer expectations for sustainable materials, ethical production, and transparent practices to build trust and loyalty. It recommended that government officials should encourage sustainable fashion practices through various incentives, as well as such awareness creation campaigns. Lastly, the consumers should be encouraged to buy according to the cultural theme of sustainability and social justice.

Keywords: Sustainable Fashion, Recycled Clothing, Cultural Values, Sustainable Consumer Behaviour, Cross-Cultural Analysis, Supply Chain Transparency.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background

In the dynamic realm of international business, the textile industry stands as a pivotal sector, influencing economies, cultures, and societies globally (Beattie et al., 2000). This industry, with its huge supply chain, wide range of markets, and complex manufacturing system, is now gaining a new era of change because of a shift to the sustainability model. This research focuses on how growing awareness of the environment and doing the right thing is forcing international business organizations to change their strategies especially with regards to cross cultural view towards Green Consumerism (Flintoft, 2009).

Sustainability in the textile industry has several perspectives namely, environmental, social and economic. In sustainable practices, this sector has few objectives that include the use of the environmentally friendly material, minimizing waste, the efficient usage of water, and energy, and fair treatment of workers at the production, supply, or distribution end (C. S. Lee & Park, 2017). Nevertheless, the effectiveness of these practices is also determined by culturing that defines consumers' perception and willingness to engage in different countries.

As with any culture or society, the approach taken when dealing with sustainable existences proves complex due to several factors such as cultural values, economic factors, and many other factors. All these attitudes play a very big role in their purchase decisions and on their attitude towards the brands (Raithel et al., 2021). For example, cases of environmental degradation and other ethical considerations have motivated client awareness in the western nations through preference of environmentally friendly products. This trend is seen through the heightened consumers' consciousness to aspects such as organic cotton, recycled materials, and products that have been certified as fair trade (Ponomareva et al., 2022).

Still, different attitudes towards sustainability could be seen in many developing countries due to their dissimilar priorities. Through pressure from personal-economic factors, the consumer

continues to pay more attention to the aspect of cost and versatility (Audretsch et al., 2021). It is significant to admit that different people can have a different level of concern and recognition of environmental and social issues and thus, when making the purchasing decision, they will take into consideration sustainability factors. It is equally important to have a realization of these cross-cultural differences that may affect the business among those in the textile market internationally (Dheer, 2024). The level of economic development in a country also plays a significant role in shaping consumer attitudes towards sustainability in the textile industry. In highly developed economies, consumers often have greater disposable income and access to information, enabling them to make informed choices about sustainable products (Evan & Holý, 2023). These markets are normally characterized by well-developed regulation that has provisions for sustaining responsible corporate behaviour hence affecting the expectations and consumer behaviour.

It is expected that in emerging economies the situation is quite different. Although there is a growing consciousness of sustainability, aspects like income, price consciousness and accessibility of sustainable products significantly affect consumers' perspective (Richieri Hanania, 2016). By and large, businesses may have to employ different techniques to introduce sustainable forms of production practices; for instance, appeal of the organization by emphasizing on the fact that, high quality and long-lasting products are more economical in the long run or social cause by undertaking patronage of local craftsmen/communities (Dheer, 2024).

The characteristics of globalisation including the movement of products, information and many other cultural factors affecting societies have had an impact on the textile industry. It has made sustainability concepts spread across the globe depending on acceptance and ease of implementation (Evan & Holý, 2023). The exploitative use of various cultures is evident with clothes manufacturing MNCs in the textile industry; they must deal with sustainable cultures like environmental conservation and cultural exigencies such as consumer tastes.

For example, international firms might have general strict sustainability standards or product promotion campaign but adjust them to fit cultural norms of the specific country. However, if sustainability is an essential factor for consumers in the markets where the brand operates, it can say more about sustainable activities in such spheres (Raithel et al., 2021). On the other hand, in the markets where other factors have more priority, they can target other aspects such as the quality and value of the product, its relevance, before advancing the topics of sustainability.

It has been evident that the search for sustainable features in the global textile is both aiding and hampering international firms. However, probably the most significant problem now is the unexpected or low commitment of various participants engaged in global supply chains. Ensuring transparency and traceability throughout the supply chain is a daunting task, yet it is essential for maintaining consumer trust and meeting regulatory requirements.

Moreover, businesses must navigate the diverse regulatory landscapes of different countries, which can vary widely in terms of environmental standards, labor laws, and sustainability requirements. This necessitates a flexible and adaptive approach to compliance and risk management.

Nevertheless, the change towards sustainability is by no means least a series of opportunities and potential points of differentiation. Bringing sustainability into the overall strategy and harmonizing the values of a company with the customer's values gives the producer an advantage, making them stand out and improve their sales (Brislin & Kim, 2003). Further, by engaging with the community groups, NGO's and other multi-stakeholders, there is also an opportunity to enhance the sustainable development of communities and the creation of value for all.

The cross-cultural consumers' perceptions are an important factor when it comes to sustainability issues of the textile industry and deserves attention from the international management of the companies (Audretsch et al., 2021). These attitudes are considerations of the cultural, economic and social factors that must be considered to formulate strategies that will appeal to different consumers out there. It is always possible to tie these concepts with sustainability and adaption to cultural experiences at the international level as such approach will improve the overall condition of the environment and social sphere in addition to long-term success of companies (Ponomareva et al., 2022). However, as the globalisation of economies advances so does the need for sustainable practice in the textile industry thus everyone's aim towards change.

Sustainable product attributes such as the type of pack, energy consumption, and material usage attract consumers' preference for sustainability (Chang and Watchravesringkan, 2018). Several specific properties directly influence the actions of the consumer, especially when it comes to influencing cross cultural adaptability of products sustainably. On the other hand, ignoring cultural differences or providing not enough options for customers' peculiarities may lead to their leaving. Customised graphics, textures, and wording strike a deep chord with culturally varied sensibilities,

building rapport and confidence. Inclusivity is promoted by customisable options and inclusive sizing, which show consideration for different needs.

1.2 Problem Statement

This research addresses the gap in understanding how cultural factors influence consumer attitudes and behaviours towards recycled clothing in the UK. Even though there is an increasing awareness of sustainability within the textile industry today, the understanding of cross-cultural consumer attitudes toward sustainable products remains underexplored. Firstly, most existing studies focus on sustainability in fashion (Mukendi et al., 2020) but lack a comparative cross-cultural perspective, limiting the generalizability of findings to specific regions or cultural contexts. Research is needed to investigate how cultural differences affect consumer perceptions of sustainability in fashion across various geographical locations.

Furthermore, a second research gap has been discovered as noted by (Wang et al., 2022), the impact of specific product features such as eco-friendly materials, durability, and ethical production on consumer attitudes has been widely studied, but there is limited knowledge on how these features are perceived differently by consumers from diverse cultural backgrounds. This gap leaves an incomplete understanding of how to tailor sustainable products to meet the unique expectations of global markets.

Thirdly, the role of socio-cultural factors such as values, traditions, and norms in shaping sustainable fashion choices is not sufficiently addressed. While studies often focus on economic or demographic factors, the nuanced influence of cultural values on sustainable consumption is under-investigated (Lee, 2014). Addressing this gap will provide deeper insights into how companies can promote sustainable fashion practices that resonate with consumers in various cultural settings, ultimately encouraging broader adoption of sustainable products in the textile industry. Stakeholders can create strategies that effectively balance affordability, consumer preferences, and environmental responsibility while promoting cross-cultural sustainable consumption by addressing these gaps.

1.3 Research Questions

This study aims to address the following question:

1. How do specific product features and cross-cultural related factors influence consumer behavior and encourage the adoption of sustainable fashion among customers from different cultural backgrounds?

1.4 Research Aim

This research aim seeks to investigate the interplay between specific product features and cultural factors in influencing consumer behavior towards the adoption of sustainable products in the textile industry. It is cannot restrict to only study the perspective of different cultural elements such as design of product, material used, displaying of the eco labels and other cultural factors that influence consumer attitude and their purchasing behaviour.

The aim includes the analysis of how specific facets of products, including using organic or recycled materials, are informants' perceptions of sustainability across cultures. It also seeks to establish the extent of confidence that the eco-labels and certifications create among cultural subgroups in the textile products.

Moreover, the purpose involves identifying the way the cultural values, norms, and beliefs influence consumers' decisions to purchase the sustainable products. It seeks to identify how factors such as individualism versus collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, and long-term orientation influence consumer attitudes towards sustainability in the textile industry. By investigating these dynamics, the aim aims to provide insights into how businesses can tailor their product offerings and marketing strategies to effectively engage consumers from diverse cultural backgrounds and promote sustainable consumption practices globally.

1.5 Research Objectives

1. To Examine the Influence of Specific Product Attributes on Cross-Cultural Consumer Behavior in Sustainable Fashion.
2. To Identify Key Cultural Factors Influencing Consumers Attitudes towards Adopting Sustainable Clothing.
3. To Assess Cross-cultural Consumer Prioritization of Environmental and Ethical Concerns.
4. To Examine Consumer Demand for Transparency in Sustainable Fashion Supply Chains.

1.6 Significance of Research

This research is significant as it provides details for textile companies, policymakers, researchers and consumers in the sustainable fashion industry. Thus, the study provides knowledge about cultural values that affects consumers' attitude toward recycled clothing to the textile companies as well as help them to a better understanding of consumer preference to develop and market appropriate products to bring innovation and loyalty. These findings can be used and implemented by policymakers to create supportive policies as well as campaigns in education towards sustainable use of resources. The paper is valuable for university scholars as it presents findings that provide new knowledge in the domain of the researched topics and define further research directions. The research empowers consumers to make informed purchasing decisions that align with their cultural and ethical values, supporting a holistic approach to sustainability in the fashion industry.

1.7 Research Methodology

The methodology of this research involved a qualitative approach to explore cross-cultural consumer attitudes towards sustainable clothing. To obtain users' qualitative data, 50 participants of various cultural backgrounds living in the UK were asked to complete semi-structured interviews with focus on their concerns, preferences, and behaviours about sustainable fashion. The interview questions developed from the research conceptual framework and literature review that aimed at assessing the extent to which culturally appropriate features of recycled clothing. Data collected from the interviews were transcribed verbatim and analysed using thematic coding. This involved open coding to identify initial categories, axial coding to explore relationships between codes, and selective coding to refine core themes. The analysis aimed to uncover patterns and themes related to environmental impact, social responsibility, cultural values, and purchasing behaviours. Ethical considerations were adhered to by ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, and reflexivity throughout the research process.

1.8 Thesis Structure

The thesis is structured into five chapters, each serving a specific purpose. Chapter One, the Introduction, provides background information on the research topic, outlining its significance and objectives. Chapter Two, the Literature Review, examines existing literature on sustainable fashion, consumer behaviour, and cultural influences, identifying key themes and gaps that inform

the study's theoretical framework. Chapter Three, Methodology describes the specifics of the research design, including the sampling plan, data analysis procedures, qualitative approach, and ethical considerations. Chapter Four, Data Analysis, presents the thematic analysis of interview data collected from participants, highlighting key themes and patterns related to consumer attitudes towards sustainable clothing and cultural influences. Chapter Five, Conclusion and Recommendations, summarizes the main findings, discusses their implications for textile companies and policymakers, and offers recommendations for future research, emphasizing the importance of cultural values in shaping sustainable fashion consumption.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Sustainability in the Textile Industry

Sustainability in the textile industry has become a critical area of focus due to the field's significant social and environmental effects. The sector is renowned for its extensive use of water, chemicals, and energy, contributing to pollution and resource depletion. As global awareness of environmental issues grows, there is increasing pressure on the textile industry to adopt sustainable practices (Kozłowski, Searcy, & Bardecki, 2015).

An important factor of sustainability that is mainly related to textiles is the usage and creation of environmentally friendly fabrics. Organic cotton, recycled fibres and bio-based materials have drawn the interest of customers usually opting for the common textile materials. These materials' goals are to further decrease environmental impacts through decreased pesticide use, waste and

carbon emissions (Shen, 2014). These materials' incorporation is likely to be paired up with the certifications and standards like GOTS and OEKOTEX that point to the environmental and social rules.

Another important factor is increasing the sustainability of various types of production. Techniques like waterless dyeing, recycling system, efficient equipment, etc. are used to reduce the harm of textile production on environment (Chen & Burns, 2006). Also, clean production practices and proper waste management become critical for reducing pollutions and enhancing resource utilization.

Consumer behaviour is also the key player in the introduction of sustainable measures in the textile industry. An increasing emphasis on professionalism is also observed where the consumer looks for a company or brand's ethical responsibility (Lombardi Netto et al., 2021). This change is evident with the appearance of slow fashion and generally, more trends such as second-hand and up cycled clothing (Hu et al., 2019). Nonetheless, there are obstacles associated with increasing consumer consciousness and readiness to spend more on eco-products, although there is a positive tendency here. CSR initiatives, or corporate social responsibility are another dimension of sustainability in textiles (Abbate et al., 2024). Companies are increasingly engaging in practices that promote fair labor, safe working conditions, and community development. Brands like Patagonia and H&M have made significant strides in integrating CSR into their business models, showcasing that sustainability can align with profitability (Perry, Wood, & Fernie, 2015).

Sustainability in the textile industry derives a large meaning from environmental consciousness of fabrics, manufacturing methods, buyers and sellers and responsibility (Piya and Berry, 2024). Some improvements have been established over time, and extra endeavours are requisite to resolve issues to deliver lasting solutions that belong to the volatility of the field of practice. Continued innovation, regulatory support, and consumer education are essential to drive this transformation (Marquesone & Carvalho, 2022).

Challenges faced by fashion executives to improving consumer perceptions of their company's sustainability credentials worldwide in 2022

2.2 Theoretical Framework of Hofstede

Understanding cross-cultural consumers' attitudes towards sustainability in the textile industry requires a robust theoretical framework that integrates concepts from cultural studies, consumer behaviour, and sustainability. Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory gives a rich background on how cultural values can be placed into perspective to determine consumers' attitude towards sustainable textiles (Khlif, 2016). This theory that was proposed by Geert Hofstede splits several indexes that are used in the explanation of the differences in the norms, values, and behaviour existing between different societies (Hofstede, 2001). These are the dimensions central to identifying consumers' perception and appreciations of sustainability across different cultures.

Based on the Hofstede's Cultural Factors, one of the most important aspects discussed is the Individualism/Collectivism factor (Grimsley, 2021). While individualistic cultures place emphasis on the individual's preferences as well as his/her independence, collectivist cultures think about the society and the mutual consent of the people in it. In relation to the sustainability in the textile industries, consumers who are easier to influence are the individual consumers from the western world such as the United State and German who have personal values regarding to production of products in a sustainable manner without affecting the environment (Soares et al., 2007). They will find those textiles which are grouped under organic or recycled brands indicating a personal concern of the environment.

On the other hand, consumers from collectivistic culture like for example consumers from China or Japan can be motivated by the sustainability drive from the view of the whole society or the community's welfare (Khlif, 2016). These consumers also appreciate product that would help the local people or create items that are culturally relevant, enhancing the conservation of the natural resources (Hofstede, 2001). For example, "There is evidence that goods that are produced fairly, for instance, textiles that support better working conditions or those that support communal development, will be readily received by cultures such as these"(Tamura, 2018).

The second dimension is Uncertainty Avoidance, which shows how much this society can accept the situations, which are described as uncertain (Grimsley, 2021). Uncertainty avoidance is high when cultures require well-defined schedules or rules and procedures; low uncertainty avoidance is experienced when cultures embrace the unknown and new ideas. With regard to the culture variables, it can be presupposed that the consumers from countries with high uncertainty avoidance

like Japan and most of the European countries might prefer the textiles that are eco-labelled or meeting highly accredited environmental standards (Hofstede and Minkov, 2010). These certifications give assurance and help remove doubts regarding the environmental effects and cost of their purchases.

Power Distance is another dimension that influences consumer attitudes towards sustainability in the textile industry. It describes the degree to which society's weaker members accept and anticipate an unequal distribution of power. High power distance cultures, like those found in parts of Asia and Latin America, may place a higher priority on sustainability programs that advance social justice and decent treatment of workers in the textile supply chain (Hofstede, 1980). Consumers in these cultures may favor textiles that are certified as fair trade or produced under ethical working conditions, aligning with their cultural values of social justice and fairness (Carrigan and Attalla 2001).

Masculinity versus Femininity is a dimension that reflects the distribution of roles between genders in society. Cultures with high masculinity emphasize assertiveness, competitiveness, and achievement, whereas those with high femininity prioritize cooperation, quality of life, and caring for others. In terms of sustainability, consumers from masculine cultures, such as the United States and Japan, may value textiles that demonstrate technological innovation or superior performance alongside sustainability credentials (Hofstede, 2011). On the other hand, consumers from feminine cultures, such as Scandinavian countries and the Netherlands, may prioritize textiles that emphasize environmental stewardship, community well-being, and ethical sourcing practices (Hofstede, 1980).

Long-Term Orientation is another dimension introduced by Hofstede, focusing on the extent to which a culture values long-term planning, perseverance, and tradition. Cultures with a long-term orientation, such as those in East Asia, may prioritize sustainability initiatives that promote environmental conservation and resource efficiency in the textile industry (Hofstede, 2001). These consumers are likely to support textiles made from renewable materials or those that have minimal impact on natural resources, aligning with their cultural values of sustainability and long-term thinking.

Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory offers a valuable framework for understanding how cultural values influence consumer attitudes towards sustainability in the textile industry (Khlif,

2016). By considering dimensions such as individualism versus collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, power distance, masculinity versus femininity, and long-term orientation, international businesses can tailor their sustainability strategies to resonate with diverse cultural preferences and consumer expectations across global markets. This approach not only enhances consumer engagement but also promotes sustainable consumption practices that respect and align with various cultural values (Grimsley, 2021).

Figure 1 Hofstede's Cultural Dimension Theory (Hofstede, 2001).

2.3 Influence of Sustainable Product Attributes across Cultures

Sustainability has become a crucial consideration for consumers worldwide, influencing their purchasing decisions across various industries, including fashion, food, and electronics (Hofstede and Minkov, 2010). However, the role that is envisaged by the customers on the various sustainable product attributes like material type, eco-labels and price is quite different across the various cultures. This literature review examines how these attributes influence consumer perceptions and

behaviours in different cultural contexts, drawing from empirical studies and market research (Chen et al., 2019).

2.3.1 Types of Materials

Cultural dimensions, as defined by frameworks like Hofstede's model, play a significant role in shaping consumer preferences for different types of materials in sustainable fashion. These dimensions help explain why certain materials may be favored by consumers from diverse cultural backgrounds (De Mooij and Hofstede, 2010).

In high power distance cultures, such as India or Mexico, consumers may prioritize materials that signal wealth and status. For example, organic silk, fine wool, or cashmere are often preferred for their association with luxury and exclusivity. These materials reflect societal hierarchies, where displaying social rank through fashion is important. In contrast, low power distance cultures like the Netherlands or Sweden favor more egalitarian approaches, where consumers are inclined toward accessible, eco-friendly materials like recycled polyester or organic cotton. These choices reflect a broader emphasis on sustainability and fairness rather than luxury.

In individualistic cultures, such as the United States or Australia, consumers tend to prioritize materials that align with personal values or self-expression (Palak Gupta & Dubey, 2016). Materials like vegan leather or innovative biodegradable fabrics are popular, as they allow individuals to make unique statements about their ethical stance on environmental issues.

Conversely, in collectivist cultures like China or Japan, materials that reflect group harmony and community well-being are more valued. For example, natural fibres like bamboo or locally sourced cotton may be preferred because they symbolize both environmental responsibility and cultural preservation (Gul et al., 2021). These materials support collective sustainability goals, reinforcing community solidarity. While high uncertainty avoidance cultures such as Portugal or South Korea, materials with proven durability, such as organic wool or sturdy hemp, are often preferred.

2.3.2 Price Sensitivity

Price is a critical factor in consumer decision-making, and its influence on the purchase of sustainable products can differ greatly across cultures (Zhang et al., 2018). Cultural differences significantly influence price sensitivity across distinctive societies, shaping consumer behaviour toward sustainable fashion.

In parts of Latin America or the Middle East pursuing high power distance cultures, consumers are often less price-sensitive if higher prices signal status or prestige. For example, eco-luxury brands using premium organic materials may be preferred as they emphasize social hierarchy and exclusivity (Ali Naqvi et al., 2018). Conversely, in low power distance cultures like Scandinavia, consumers may be more price-sensitive, focusing on fairness and accessibility. Affordable, sustainable fashion is often valued more, as it aligns with egalitarian principles.

In individualistic cultures such as the United States or the UK, price sensitivity is moderate. Consumers may pay a premium for sustainable products if they resonate with personal values, such as eco-friendliness or ethical production. For instance, they might be willing to spend more on vegan leather because it supports their individual identity and beliefs (Whitaker, 2021).

Meanwhile, in collectivist cultures Japan or South Korea, price sensitivity may be lower when purchases benefit the community or society. For example, buying locally sourced, eco-friendly clothing might be seen as supporting collective environmental goals, leading consumers to accept higher prices for the greater goods. In high uncertainty avoidance country Greece, consumers are more price-sensitive, preferring established brands that ensure long-term durability and reduce perceived risks (AlAli, 2019).

2.3.3 Eco-Labels and Certifications

Products eco-labels or certifications also act as a mean of letting the consumer know the sustainability of the products. However, it can be realized that the outcome of these medicines differs depending on the culture of a particular society (Richards et al., 2022). In Europe, EU Eco-label and the Fair-Trade labels are familiar to the consumers and are deemed credible. The following labels offer guarantees of the environmental and social performances of goods and largely impact the buying behaviour (Testa et al., 2015). Comparing these elements in different cultures shows that in those countries where legislation and consumers' attitudes toward

sustainability are not very well developed, the level of recognition and the trust in eco-labels can also be lower. For example, most African and some Southeast Asian nations have witnessed a situation where several actual goodie eco-labels, but with no accurate standard parameters for the use of the labels, consumers are likely to develop a sort of healthy scepticism about the labels (D'Souza et al., 2006). This may take together; this can dilute the perception of consumers regarding the eco-labels and thus decrease their usefulness in influencing the market towards green products (Kanz et al., 2023).

In addition, the efficiency of eco-labels is also dependent on the same consumer's environmental literacy. Highly environmentally sensitive cultures are influenced by detailed information on the sustainability of products which is displayed concerning to the eco-labels. On the other hand, in the cultures with less sensitivity of environmental problems, straightforward appeals to the self-interest of the consumers regarding the advantages of buying environmentally friendly products might be more persuasive (Sammer & Wüstenhagen, 2006). This means that relativities in the sustainable product attributes like price for the product, type of material used, and eco-labels differs from one culture to another depending on the economic status of the country, culture and environmental awareness of the community. It is important that these cultural issues are met to ensure that firms that dealing in the exportation of sustainable products have the right methods of doing so. Thus, understanding how consumers in different locations can be managed and the steps companies can take to overcome constraints including price sensitivity and scepticism about green labels, the food industries can continue to meet the needs of various consumer groups and thus assist in helping to foster world sustainability. Increased consumer consciousness means that client solutions can only be successful in the long run if cultural differences in the subject of sustainability are regarded as essential (Jayashree & Priya, 2019).

2.4 Sustainable Fashion and Cross-cultural Consumer Behaviour

According to the 1987 report by (The United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development, Brundtland,) sustainability is commonly understood to involve social, environmental, and economic factors in order to preserve the environment for future generations. In terms of textile, sustainability is defined by (Joergens, 2006, p. 361) as "affordable clothing that

incorporates fair trade principles with sweatshop-free labour conditions while utilising organic and biodegradable cotton to minimise harm to the environment and workers."

The best way to understand sustainability is to break it down into distinct parts and concentrate on how sustainable initiatives affect society. These elements, which stand for the social, environmental, and economic foundations of sustainability, are referred to as the three distinguishing bases (General assembly of the United Nations, 2005). Moreover, (Sheth, Sethia, and Srinivas 2011) stated that each pillar examines the effect of consumption on the pillar's well-being from the viewpoint of cross-cultural consumers. Elkington (1999) created the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) model, which combines the three bases of sustainability and is a more organisational model of sustainability measurement. Companies can influence consumers' attitudes and behaviours in the future by acting in line with their understanding of the cross-consumer position on sustainability, according to research by (McNeill and Moore, 2015) and (Park and Kim, 2016). In their study on the consumer-centric view of sustainable fashion, Park and Kim (2016) make clear that a firm must integrate all three sustainability pillars into its business operations. If not, a company's sustainability initiatives may have a detrimental effect on the company's reputation among consumers (ibid). Still, Fulton and Lee (2013) show that businesses in the clothing sector prioritize the environmental and social dimensions of sustainability, with the economic pillar receiving the least attention.

2.4.1 Social Responsibility

The prominent factor that can affect consumers' needs for sustainable products are factors of social responsibility. Also, many cultures can be mentioned, such as the Nordic countries or the Scandinavian Peninsula, including Sweden and Denmark, where the values of social justice and legal morality are given a special place. Consumers in these regions will be more willing to purchase products that are affiliated to fair labour, community and ethical practices. For instance, such countries' consumers' awareness of the Fair-Trade products is an epitome of their inherent culture of justice for producer segments (Testa et al., 2015).

On the other hand, in the cultures where the economic development plays the leading role, such as in many African and SE Asian nations, may be more focused on how sustainable products can assist in local economic development and uplift the living quality. The consumers in these regions may also prefer to buy products which are locally produced and help in employment of their fellow

citizens. It is prescribed how the objective is often to portray sustainable products' returns to their proximate milieus (Kumar & Noble, 2016).

2.4.2 Environmental Awareness

Culture has a unique impact on the level of awareness of consumers regarding the environment, and thus the acceptable level of sustainability for purchasable products. Thus, the key feature of many countries in Western Europe and North America is a relatively high level of environmental awareness (Funk et al., 2021). Consumers in those regions can be said to be sensitive to the environment and are willing to pay considerably more for products that are environmentally sound such as product made from organic or recycled material. For example, Connell (2010) identified that the consumers in United States of America and Europe had tendency to patronize sustainable apparels with aim of being environmentally friendly.

On the other hand, many developing countries of the world have not yet woken up to the cause of environment consciousness although it is gradually emerging at a slow pace (Ahmad et al., 2024). It can also be added that the fast urbanization and industrialization rates in the countries like India and China have bring significant deterioration of the environmental situation; the concern grows. Nevertheless, their main emphasis stays local, being oriented to such domestic topics as air and water pollution, while global and sustainable themes are still not popular there (Gupta & Ogden, 2009). Consequently, consumers in such cultures may be inclined towards socially responsible goods tackling first order environmental problems in the locality.

2.4.3 Economic Considerations

Nothing is more vital in consumers' decisions and inclinations towards sustainable production than the element of this economic factor in different cultures and the economy (Krugman et al., 2018). Another major challenge affecting the adoption of sustainable products is that the consumers mainly in the developed countries have the discretionary income and hence they are willing to pay for the sustainable products. The studies show that buyer in the countries such as Germany and United States are willing to pay a premium for the products, which are environment and ethically produced (Horne, 2009).

However, there is one critical constraint in the lower income countries, which is the question of cost implication in the use of the sustainable products. They spend more of their income on the basic needs, or very little to extend on the purchases, hence are not sensitive to environmentally

friendly products. In a study elaborated by (D'Souza et al, 2006) concerning sustainable consumption in numerous developing markets, the authors noted that although there are ever-growing sensibilities about sustainability, costs attached to these sustainable products erect a major barrier to their purchase (Marais et al., 2022). Thus, there is a need to have solutions that can lower the cost of sustainable products so that it can meet the market demands of these areas.

2.4.4 Influence of Local Values and Traditions

Consumer behaviour regarding the use of sustainable products is largely determined by culture and orientation of a specific geographical region. Similarly, in Japan consumers embrace the cultural aspect of *Motional* which is a feeling of regret over waste which makes the consumers to have a preference for products that are long lasting and made with an aspect of sustainability in mind (Niinimäki, 2010). In the same way, the cultural values of collectivism prevalent in Latin America encourage peoples' consumption of products, which assist in sustaining the crafters and traditional cultural practices.

The African people also have frequent relations with the land and with natural resources; therefore, they will abide by such products that reflect concern over the sustainable supply of vital ecology systems. Infrastructure that embodies this harmonious relationship between culture and nature opens a prospect of markets for sustainable products and services enjoyed socially without excluding the economic aspect if made affordable (D'Souza et al., 2006).

Consumers' sensitivity levels to environmental concern, social conscience, and concerns that emanate from economic developmental differences pose a considerable impact on their market perception of sustainable products (Al-Hiyari et al., 2023). Knowledge about these culture-biases is paramount if the targeted firms are to market sustainable products in the international markets. Thus, understanding cultural relevance and economic limitations can help companies to always meet customers' needs all over the world contributing to the achievement of global sustainability objectives. Since the consumers' awareness of the sustainable products is gradually increasing, it would be pertinent to note that the internationalization of sustainable culture practices would go a long way to help in the achievement of the overall goals of sustainable products.

2.5 Cross-cultural Differences and Sustainable Purchase

Cross-cultural differences significantly influence consumer behaviours and preferences in the purchase of sustainable textile products. These differences are shaped by a complex interplay of

cultural values, economic conditions, and communication styles, all of which play crucial roles in determining consumer attitudes towards sustainability in the textile industry (Gelfand et al., 2007).

Cultural values have a profound impact on how consumers perceive and prioritize sustainability in their purchasing decisions. Currently, a culture that is most dominant is the Western culture, especially the American culture and those of the European Union countries, where every individual is under obligation to protect the environment (Lifintsev & Wellbrock, 2019). Consumers in these regions remain conscious about the environmentally friendly products in the market and those that are labelled organic such as organic cotton products, other related products that are made from recycled materials (Connell, 2010). This is due to consumers' consideration of the culture concerning the environment as well as the personal concern of the individuals with their ecological impacts (Sahadevan & Sumangala, 2021).

On the other hand, in many Asian countries people's sustainable purchasing behaviour is determined by collective values and social norms (Panina & Kroumova, 2015). A higher understanding of the concept of sustainability is observed in Asian countries like Japan and South Korea due to cultural reference to fractal theory where nature is in harmony with the community. Consumers in these regions are paying more attention to the textiles that are produced using local craftsmanship and the techniques that are part of the traditions with the cultural aspect complementing the environmental aspect in terms of its consideration (Kumar, & Noble 2016).

Concerning the economic factors affecting consumer behaviours of sustainable textile products, it should also be noted that economic factors have a great influence on consumer decisions. Consumers in developed countries' economies have relatively higher purchasing power and are willing to spend a premium amount on the products that are eco-friendly. Another market, which shows its potential in sustainable textiles, includes German and Scandinavia markets, which reveals the quality of sustainable textiles and ethical considerations from the consumers. It provided economic capacity for the establishment of markets for strong textiles and fostered business endeavours that tries to minimize impacts on the environment.

However, in the developing countries and the regions with relatively low standards of living the economic factors are the main limitations to the widespread use of sustainable textiles (Y.-T. Lee & Gyamfi, 2022). Regarding these markets, consumers are likely to be more sensitive to the price

and may prefer cheap products irrespective of the sustainability aspect as they are generally of low purchasing power (Gupta & Ogden, 2009). However, there is a growing awareness of environmental issues, and initiatives to promote sustainable textiles through partnerships and educational campaigns are gaining traction, albeit slowly.

Communication styles also play a critical role in influencing consumer perceptions and behaviours towards sustainable textiles. In Western cultures, consumers rely heavily on clear and transparent information, including eco-labels and certifications, to guide their purchasing decisions. These labels provide assurance of a product's environmental credentials and help consumers make informed choices (Sammer & Wüstenhagen, 2006). Effective communication strategies that highlight the environmental benefits of sustainable textiles, such as reduced water usage or lower carbon footprints, resonate well with environmentally conscious consumers in these regions.

In contrast, in many Asian and African cultures, where communal values and oral traditions are prominent, storytelling and community endorsements are often more effective than technical details. Consumers in these regions value products that contribute positively to local communities and support sustainable livelihoods (D'Souza et al., 2006). Marketing strategies that emphasize social responsibility and community impact are therefore more persuasive in these cultural contexts, fostering trust and loyalty among consumers.

Another aspect of consumers' perception about sustainable textiles is the fact that the expectations about the textiles differ from culture to culture (Luna & Gupta, 2001). In western countries particularly consumers are becoming more sensitive to issues of supply chain and have forced companies through protests and legal suits to offer explanation on certain supplies.

The customers also hold brands to account for exercising ethical purchasing of raw materials and being responsible for the environment as these factors determine their consumer choice (Testa et al., 2015). On the other hand, consumers in cultures that value artisans and craft will appreciate products that support the culture and encourage the craftsmen's economy, and sustainability may be viewed as preserving culture and creating value. In conclusion, cross-cultural differences significantly influence consumer behaviours and preferences towards sustainable textile products. Cultural values, economic conditions, and communication styles shape how consumers perceive and prioritize sustainability in their purchasing decisions (Sahadevan & Sumangala, 2021). Businesses aiming to market sustainable textiles globally must tailor their strategies to align with

cultural norms, economic realities, and communication preferences of diverse consumer segments. By understanding and addressing these factors, businesses can effectively engage consumers, promote sustainable consumption, and drive positive environmental and social impacts (Lifintsev & Wellbrock, 2019).

2.6 Globalization and Cultural Convergence

In general, culture can be defined by focusing on its two main traits: shared and learned (Fischer, 2009). Based on this, the definition of culture is "the rich complex of meanings, beliefs, practices, symbols, norms, and values prevalent among people in a society." by (Schwartz, 2006, p. 138).

Globalization has significantly impacted cultural convergence, influencing consumer attitudes towards sustainability in the textile industry. This refers to the social process through which various cultural features merge to form one single culture to the extent of influencing consumers' behaviour across the globe (Gelfand et al., 2007).

Globalization as one of the causes of cultural clustering is the spread of Anglo-Saxon materialistic culture in different parts of the world. Some of the developed nations in the western world especially those in Europe and North America have played key roles in enhancing sustainable actions in functions such as textiles. There is focus on environmental conservation and ethical standards of production and this has placed pressure on the clients and the market in regard to the kind of textile products they require as pointed out by (Horne, 2009).

For example, the schemes including eco-labelling and certification levelling, like EU Eco-label or Fair-Trade certifications, are now known all over the world as the symbols of eco-friendly and ethical production. These labels offer a guarantee to the consumer around the globe regarding their purchases' effect on the environment and society (Sammer & Wüstenhagen, 2006).

Furthermore, the actual globalization that has taken place in recent decades has also provided for the sharing of information and ideas pertaining to the implementation of sustainability programs (Sahadevan & Sumangala, 2021). Multilateral organizations and NGOs are significant in advancing countries' sustainability guidelines as well as sharing information and best practices worldwide. For example, there are attempts to globalize such standards as GOTS (Global Organic Textile Standard) that unites similar worldwide initiatives and stimulates sustainability and transparency in textile production (Testa et al., 2015).

However, while globalization promotes cultural convergence, it also sparks cultural resistance and adaptation (Lifintsev & Wellbrock, 2019). Local cultures and traditions often shape how global sustainability trends are interpreted and adopted. In many Asian nations, including South Korea and Japan, traditional values of craftsmanship and respect for nature influence sustainable consumption patterns (Kumar & Noble, 2016). Consumers in these regions may prioritize products that support local artisans and traditional techniques, blending global sustainability principles with local cultural values.

Indeed, cultural globalization has played a very dramatic role in change of consumers' perception towards sustainable culture in textile industry. Although the global sustainability standards are influenced by the western practices and principles, the local cultural factors cannot be disregarded in 'constructing' the norms (Gelfand et al., 2007). Knowledge of such trends is useful for organizations that wish to conduct operations across national borders and be able to service customers in multiple ways. By embracing global sustainability standards while respecting local cultural values, businesses can foster consumer trust, enhance brand reputation, and promote sustainable practices on a global scale (Dong & Liu, 2010).

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This research aims to explore how product features and cross-cultural factors shape consumer behaviour and drive the adoption of sustainable fashion among various cultural groups through a qualitative analysis research methodology. That is why to make my work more objective and powerful, I use qualitative analysis, which helps me provide profound and comprehensive understanding of cross-cultural consumers' experiences, outlook, and difficulties towards sustainable product adaptation (Patton, 1987). The methodology is displayed below and includes information on data collection, sampling strategy, data analysis and ethics.

3.2 Research Philosophy

Explanative is a research philosophy that focuses on understanding the subjective meanings and interpretations that individuals attach to their experiences and social phenomena (Dudovskiy,

2024). While positivism looks for factual, measurable data by focusing on the causes of phenomena, exhibitive, on the other hand, pays attention to contextual details, perceptions as well as expectations of the participants (Junjie and Yingxin, 2022). This approach acknowledges that reality is constructed sociologically, and that the researchers' task is to understand the purposes people give to events in their cultural and social settings.

The present study employs Interpretivism to understand how culture impacts consumers' perception on sustainable garment. This approach is fully incorporated in this study with the aim of getting the participants' insight and perception about sustainable fashion. The scope of the study lies in identifying the underlying driving forces involved in consumers' behaviours that are not necessarily explicitly coded such as culture, values and references.

Semi structured interviews are self-explanatory, where the participants are allowed to say what they think and feel in their own way enabling the researcher to analyse these responses considering participant's cultural background. This interpretivist approach facilitates a richer understanding of the motivations behind sustainable fashion choices, highlighting the complexity of consumer attitudes and the significance of cultural influences (Irshaidat, 2022).

3.3 Research Approach

A qualitative approach is a research methodology that focuses on understanding human behaviour, experiences, and social phenomena through the collection and analysis of non-numerical data like interviews, focus groups and open-ended survey responses (Weyant, 2022). This approach seeks to provide rich, detailed insights into the complexities of participants' thoughts, feelings and motivations, rather than relying on quantifiable measurements (Lochmiller, 2021). Quantitative research focuses on the frequency, numbers, categories, and percentages while qualitative research often incorporates the context and meaning of respondents' answers, enabling researchers to investigate semiotics various aspects of the subject matter (Sardana et al., 2023).

In this current study, a qualitative research method is used to explore cross-cultural consumers' behaviours and their reasons when it comes to sustainable fashion. Semi-structured interviews with participants from various cultural backgrounds will be used in the study and the study objectives are to identify participants' perception, attitude and past experiences with recycled clothing.

This approach is particularly suitable for this research as it allows participants to express their thoughts and feelings in their own words, providing a deeper insight into how cultural values

influence their sustainable fashion choices (Creswell, 2020). The qualitative method facilitates the exploration of themes such as environmental consciousness, social responsibility and cultural norms.

3.4 Data Collection

Interviews are semi-structured to gather perspectives, experiences, and opinions from cross-cultural sustainable consumers in the UK. Interviews were selected for this research due to their ability to provide in-depth insights into the subjective experiences, explanative and opinions of cross-cultural sustainable consumers regarding recycled clothing. The interviews were carried out with the participants with different cultural backgrounds from different regions of the UK to get the general perception of different cultures regarding sustainable fashion. The participants were purposely selected through social media, relevant communities, groups, and associations that deal with sustainability and fashion.

The sample comprised 50 individuals who identified as sustainable consumers with a deliberate focus on obtaining a diverse range of cultural perspectives. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants who met specific criteria engagement in sustainable fashion practices and representation of different cultural backgrounds. The selected population included individuals from various age groups, socioeconomic backgrounds, and ethnicities, contributing to a richer understanding of the topic under investigation.

3.5 Data Analysis

In the analysis of interview data regarding consumer attitudes towards recycled clothing, several key themes and codes emerged. The first theme Concern, the codes as Environmental Impact, Labor Conditions, Transparency, Durability and Affordability reflecting participants' primary worries about sustainable textile products. The second theme Purchase Factors highlighted participants' desires for sustainable practices from textile companies with codes like Quality, Price, Sustainable materials, Low carbon footprint, Social responsibility, Ethical production, Fair trade and so on emphasizing the factors participants consider when making purchasing decisions.. The third theme focused on Cultural Influence, revealing codes such as Sustainability, Thriftiness, Environmental Stewardship, Social Status, Tradition, Sentimentality showcasing how cultural values shape attitudes towards sustainable clothing. The fourth theme is Usage Pattern incorporated codes like Quality, Personal Values, Re-using items, Purchase Frequency and

Seasonal Buying Patterns, detailing how often consumers buy sustainable products. The fifth theme Purchase Drivers, coding Environmental concern, Quality, Personal values, Cost-effectiveness, Ethical considerations, Societal norms Cultural traditions, Cultural Values focusing how cultural and personal factors drive purchasing decisions for sustainable textiles. These themes collectively illustrate the multifaceted perspectives of cross-cultural consumers regarding sustainable fashion, emphasizing the interplay between individual values, cultural norms and purchasing behaviours (Panina & Kroumova, 2015).

3.6 Research Ethics

Informed Consent: Participants were informed of the goals, procedures, benefits, and risks of the study prior to data collection. Informed consent was requested from each part of team to guarantee that participation is voluntary. Participants in the research have their identities and personal information protected and anonymously stored. Maintaining reflexivity involves self-reflection and open communication with a research supervisor or peer.

Chapter 4: Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Depth-Interviews

To accomplish this research 50 participants of different cultural backgrounds were interviewed to assess their perception towards the sustainable clothes. The interview questions focused on consumers' cultural beliefs, and he/she acts in ways that determines their limit towards sustainable design or fashion consumption. These questions were derived from the research conceptual framework and literature with the purpose of acquiring more insight into how culture influences, appreciate and the utilisation of recycled textiles in consumers' daily lives. Some of the questions incorporated in the interview focused on participants' analysis of recycled clothing in the light of cultural norms and beliefs. This approach made it possible to have intensive, extensive and immersive views on how the cultures of different societies their values help. Interview data will be analyzed with the help of thematic coding is a theoretical framework approach according to the methodology and implies searching themes in qualitative materials (Vaismoradi et al., 2016). Selective coding is based on the core categories that appear most influential for consumer attitudes

towards recycled clothes and giving a brief on how the cultural meanings intertwine with the environmental consciousness and the values that inform people’s choices. Interview questions are presented in appendices (see appendix 2).

4.1.1 Codes

Coding is a heuristic technique for figuring out the meanings of different data sections. In qualitative data analysis, a code is typically a word or brief phrase that designates a summative, salient, essence-capturing, or evocative attribute for a section of textual or visual data in a symbolic manner. (Leavy, 2014, p. 584).The data collected during interviews uses the following codes: Country Initials:

[NA/CA], [NA/US], [EU/UK], [EU/DE], [EU/FR], [AS/IN], [AS/JP], [AS/CN], [SA/BR], [SA/AR], [AU/AU], [AF/ZA].

Table 4. 1 Concern relating to textile products

Source: (Own Production, 2024)

Theme	Interview Questions	Codes
Concern	What are your main concerns or priorities when it comes to sustainable textile products?	[NA/CA], [EU/UK], [AS/JP], [SA/BR], [AU/AU] Environmental impact, Labor conditions, Transparency, Durability, Affordability, Organic materials, Product lifecycle, Certifications, Social impact, Energy consumption
Initiative	What sustainable initiatives would you like to see more from textile companies?	[NA/US], [EU/FR], [AS/CN], [SA/AR], [AF/ZA] Water reduction, Renewable energy, Transparency reports, Recycling programs, Organic materials, Fair wages, Environmental collaborations, Certifications, Educational campaigns, Product durability

Based on the analysis of the collected data, it is concluded that consumers’ activity and their approaches, preferences, and concerns when it comes to sustainable textile products cover a rather

vast spectrum. The social issues of concern include violation of workers’ rights, high rate of occupational health risks, water pollution, and carbon emissions. Customers care much about fair employment practices; it is especially important to name all the parties participating in the process of production and environmental friendliness of materials used. When it comes to appreciation of activities, consumers would like textile firms in order to reduce water consumption, embrace renewable energy sources and come up with disclosure reports. Recycling programs, the utilization of organic/biodegradable products and ensuring the provision of fair wages is highly regarded.

Table 4. 2 Purchasing factors relating to textile products

Source: (Own Production, 2024)

Theme	Interview Question	Codes
Purchasing Factor	What factors do you consider most important when buying textile products (e.g., types of materials, price, quality, environmental impact, social responsibility)? Rate the factors and their importance	[NA/CA], [NA/US], [EU/UK], [EU/DE], [EU/FR], [AS/IN] Quality, Price, Affordability, Environmental impact, Sustainable materials, Low carbon footprint, Social responsibility, Ethical production, Fair trade
	Are there any specific sustainable textile brands or products that you prefer, and why?	[AS/JP], [AS/CN], [SA/BR], [SA/AR], [AU/AU], [AF/ZA] Transparency, Organic materials, Brand commitment to sustainability, Fair labor practices, Lifecycle analysis

Analysis of the responses presented important themes. Product Quality emerged as a top consideration with respondents emphasizing durability and longevity. Many valued Environmental Impact preferring products made from sustainable materials with minimal carbon footprints and water preservation efforts. Sustainability is equally important with consumers prioritizing brands

that uphold ethical production practices and fair-trade principles. To illustrate, based on the stock-keeping-point answers, the most preferred brands are those that act under Transparency in their supply chain and production such as Stella McCartney for vegan fashion. Other brands that received appreciation and recognition for being environment friendly and that have clear and easily understandable price structures include Patagonia and Ever Lane. These preferences present a growing consumer demand for textiles that link with personal values of quality, sustainability and ethical responsibility.

Table 4. 3 Cultural influence related to recycled clothes

Source: (Own Production, 2024)

Theme	Interview Questions	Codes
Cultural Influence	How do you think your cultural background and values influence your attitudes towards sustainable clothes? Provide examples.	[NA/CA], [EU/FR], [AS/JP], [SA/BR], [AU/AU], Sustainability, Thriftiness, Cultural Heritage, Social Status, Environmental Stewardship, Sentimentality.

Environmental stewardship ranks highest, as sustainability is ingrained in consumers values, motivating them to choose eco-friendly options. Thriftiness is also crucial, as it appreciates saving money while reducing waste. Cultural heritage plays a role, as traditional beliefs in resourcefulness make recycled clothes appealing. Sentimentality adds meaning to reusing garments, especially those passed down or with personal significance. Social status is less important, but still consider how recycled fashion reflects cultural values. Sustainability and cultural ties drive preferences,

with thriftiness and sentimentality supporting the choice. The congregation of cultural norms was seen to have a main role in tradition of frugality and utilization of second-hand clothes due to promotion of reuse of material.

Table 4. 4 Usage pattern relating to textile products

Source: (Own Production, 2024)

Theme	Interview Question	Codes
Usage Pattern	How often do you purchase sustainable products like organic cotton shirts or recycled polyester jackets?	[NA/US], [EU/DE], [AS/CN], [SA/BR], [AU/AU], [AF/ZA] Purchase frequency, Seasonal buying patterns, Usage context

The interview explains the frequency and patterns of purchasing products like organic cotton shirts or recycled polyester jackets revealing various consumer attitude and courageous. Another theme category which cropped out with the respondents was purchase frequency in regard to new shirts made of organic cotton was once or sometimes in a year so as to change their wardrobe with better sustainable products. Seasonal buying patterns were important with many preferring to buy recycled polyester jackets seasonally when needed for specific weather conditions.

Table 4. 5 Cultural influences and purchasing drivers of textile products

Source: (Own Production, 2024)

Theme	Interview Questions	Codes
Purchase Drivers	What is your main reason for buying eco-friendly products like organic cotton shirts or recycled polyester jackets?	[NA/US], [EU/DE], [AS/CN], [SA/BR], [AU/AU] Environmental concern, Quality, Personal values, Cost-effectiveness, Ethical considerations, Product attributes
Cultural Influence	Do you feel that community and societal norms in your culture support the purchase of sustainable textile products?	[EU/DE], [AS/JP], [NA/US], [AF/ZA] Community norms, Societal norms
Cultural Alignment	How important is it for you that sustainable products align with your cultural traditions and values?	[AS/CN], [SA/BR], [EU/FR], [AF/ZA] Cultural traditions, Cultural values

Environmental concern emerged as a primary driver, with many participants prioritizing products that minimize carbon footprints and environmental impact. For example, organic cotton shirts were valued for their quality, comfort, and softness. Personal values, such as sustainability and ethical considerations, showed high alignment with consumer behaviors, reflecting a strong congruence between values and purchasing decisions. Cost-effectiveness, ethical labor practices, and durability were also influential, highlighting a balance between economic and ethical considerations in sustainable fashion choices. Additionally, community and societal norms played a role, reinforcing cultural values that support environmentally responsible consumption.

4.2 Discussion of the Results

This analysis of interview data from 50 participants across diverse cultural backgrounds convey consumer perceptions about recycled garments as a depiction of how culture influences consumers' behaviour in purchasing sustainably produced clothes. Research objectives are constructed clearly to investigate significant components of consumer attitude in this respect. Participants across

different cultural backgrounds expressed a strong concern about sustainability emphasizing the environmental impact, ethical labour conditions, transparency in supply chains, the use of organic materials and cultural values as paramount considerations when purchasing textile products.

4.2.1: Theme 1: Concern

Participants across different cultural backgrounds demonstrated strong concern for sustainability, particularly focusing on environmental impact, ethical labor conditions, supply chain transparency, and the use of organic materials. These findings support the first research objective: understanding consumer expertise and concerns about sustainable textiles from a cross-cultural perspective. Contrary to (McNeill and Moore's, 2015) study on consumers of sustainable fashion, the participants are aware of the sustainable intentions of the companies and are able to give examples, such as recycling programs, organic cotton clothing lines that are sustainable, better working conditions, and the implementation of laws prohibiting child labour. Participants from Western cultures (e.g., the UK) consistently emphasized ethical labor conditions and transparency in supply chains, aligning with a strong cultural focus on human rights, fair trade, and corporate social responsibility. This reflects the findings of (Carrigan and Attalla 2001), who explain that Western consumers, particularly in developed nations, are more focused on the ethical practices of companies, including labor conditions and transparency. From an international business perspective, these Western concerns highlight a growing demand for ethical compliance and transparent global supply chains, particularly in the textile industry. Companies operating in Western markets are increasingly required to adhere to international labor standards, and those that fail to do so risk damaging their brand reputation and losing market share (Loo and Davies, 2006).

In contrast, participants from Asian cultures (e.g., Japan, India and China) placed greater emphasis on environmental impact, particularly regarding water conservation and natural resource management. A Japanese consumer stated, "It's crucial that brands focus on reducing their environmental footprint," underscoring a collective responsibility toward sustainability, as highlighted by (Chan 2001). These concerns are deeply rooted in cultural values around environmental stewardship and resource conservation. Asian consumers, according to (Minton et al., 2018), prioritize sustainability in their purchasing decisions, driven by a cultural responsibility to preserve resources for future generations. In international business, this means firms targeting Asian markets must prioritize environmental sustainability initiatives, such as water-efficient

production methods and sustainable resource use, to align with local consumer expectations and enhance their market positioning. This cultural focus creates both challenges and opportunities for businesses looking to operate globally across different cultural dimensions.

4.2.2 Theme 2: Purchasing Factors

A significant number of the countries acknowledged the value of quality, but its weight varied among them. In North America (NA/CA, NA/US) and Europe (EU/UK, EU/DE, EU/FR), quality and environmental impact are top prioritized. Consumers in these regions favor sustainable, eco-friendly and recycled organic materials with a low carbon footprint, even at a higher price (Spiegel and Meadows, 2010). For example, German (EU/DE) consumers are particularly drawn to social responsibility and ethical production, driving demand for brands like Patagonia and People Tree, which emphasize transparency and fair trade practices. Moreover, the French clarify that following a scandal involving child labour, customers in France refrained from purchasing from H&M, reinforcing the previously exposed attitudes in the sector. According to (Darley et al., 2013), this scandal may have had an effect on their beliefs and motivations, causing them to reject the boycott in favour of potentially more socially sustainable options.

In Asia (AS/IN), price and affordability play a more prominent role as Indian consumers seek sustainable options but balance them with cost-effectiveness. Contrary to (Yarrow and O'Donnell's, 2009) research, the Chinese considered quality primarily as style durability and desire towards fashion items that are made for long-lasting use. These attitudes, which emphasise the future by longing timeless and sustainable clothing (Hofstede and Minkov, 2010), are consistent with China's high LTO (de Mooij, 2011). However, there is growing interest in environmental impact and ethical production, especially in urban centres where brands like No Nasties are emerging. Furthermore, Latin America (SA/BR, SA/AR), consumers prioritize social responsibility and fair labor practices, favoring brands like Veja, known for fair trade and support for local artisans. Similarly, in Australia (AU/AU) and Africa (AF/ZA), consumers focus on brand commitment to sustainability, preferring brands like Outland Denim and Indigenous Clothing, which highlight ethical production and transparency. These cultural differences shape global strategies, requiring international businesses to adapt to local preferences. Western markets demand premium,

sustainable products, while Asian markets emphasize affordability, making localized product offerings and ethical transparency crucial for global success.

4.2.3 Theme 3: Cultural Influence

Cultural influences emerged as a significant theme, addressing the third research objective by illustrating how diverse cultural backgrounds impact attitudes towards recycled clothing. Cultural influences significantly shape attitudes toward sustainable clothing, as evidenced by Hofstede's dimensions of culture (Hofstede, 2001). In Japan (AS/JP), where thriftiness and environmental stewardship are highly valued, concepts like "mottainai" drive positive perceptions of recycled clothing. Participants from Japan often view purchasing recycled clothing as a reflection of cultural heritage and wise resource use, reinforcing sustainable practices as a social norm. A Japanese consumer expressed, "Buying recycled clothing is not just sustainable; it's a way to honor our resources," illustrating a strong cultural connection to thriftiness and environmental stewardship. This aligns with Hofstede's emphasis on long-term orientation, reflecting a cultural inclination towards sustainability and resourcefulness (Tamura, 2018). Conversely, in regions with high power distance and a strong emphasis on social status, such as Middle Eastern countries, there is a tendency to associate recycled clothing with lower social status and inferior quality. Schlosser et al. (2006) note that in these societies, the desire for luxury and brand loyalty often overshadows environmental considerations. Alserhan (2010) further emphasizes that the cultural focus on exclusivity and newness leads to reluctance in adopting recycled clothing. A consumer from this region confessed, "Wearing recycled clothes feels like a step down; I prefer luxury brands," demonstrating a cultural tendency to prioritize status over sustainability (Schlosser et al., 2006). In those cultures, status plays an immense part and buying second-hand clothing are looked down upon. (de Mooij and Hofstede, 2010; Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010). This illustrates the challenge for international brands in such markets, where exclusivity and luxury overshadow environmental concerns.

In North America (NA/CA) and Europe (EU/FR), cultural attitudes vary; sustainability is often linked to social responsibility and personal values, while Australia (AU/AU) embraces a blend of these perspectives, highlighting environmental stewardship and community values. An Australian consumer proudly stated, "I choose recycled clothing because it reflects my values," emphasizing

the connection between personal beliefs and purchasing decisions. This aligns with the popularity of eco-conscious brands like Patagonia, where consumers seek products that reflect personal beliefs (Hofstede, 1980). These cross-cultural differences underline the necessity for international businesses to adapt their marketing strategies to align with local cultural values, ensuring the promotion of sustainable textiles resonates with diverse consumer attitudes.

4.2.4 Theme 4: Usage Pattern

The interview findings on purchasing frequency for sustainable products like organic cotton shirts and recycled polyester jackets highlight significant variations influenced by cultural dimensions. For instance, in North America, characterized by individualism, a respondent noted, “I only buy new organic shirts once or twice a year; it’s about making choices that fit my budget.” This reflects Hofstede’s (1980) idea that personal choice and cost considerations drive purchasing habits in individualistic societies, resulting in lower purchase frequency.

In contrast, a participant from Asia stated, “I usually buy a recycled jacket when the weather changes; it’s practical and aligns with my community values.” This emphasis on seasonal buying patterns showcases a collectivist culture where purchases are made based on necessity and environmental stewardship, as highlighted by Chan (2001).

Additionally, brand loyalty is evident when a South African respondent remarked, “I stick to brands that prioritize sustainability because I want to support ethical practices.” This aligns with findings from (Minton et al. 2018), indicating that consumers are more likely to remain loyal to brands reflecting their sustainability values. Understanding these crucial diverse usage contexts enables international businesses to adapt their marketing engagement effectively, catering to varied consumer preferences across cultures.

4.2.5 Theme 5: Purchase Drivers

The research also focuses on the crucial drivers that influence cross-cultural consumer’s behaviour for buying sustainable products, such as organic cotton shirts and recycled polyester jackets, reveal significant cross-cultural differences influenced by Hofstede's cultural dimensions. In Scandinavian countries, characterized by high levels of individualism and low power distance,

consumers often demonstrate a strong commitment to environmental concerns. A Swedish (EU/FR) interviewee told, “I buy sustainable clothing regularly because it incorporates with my values and helps combat climate change.” This behaviour resonates with (Thøgersen and Schrader’s 2012) findings that highlight the intrinsic motivation of Scandinavian consumers to prioritize sustainability in their purchasing decisions.

Conversely, Southern European consumers, often facing economic challenges and demonstrate different motivations. A Spanish consumer said, “I want to buy sustainable clothes, but I need to consider my budget first.” This perspective aligns with Hofstede's dimension of uncertainty avoidance (Hofstede, 2010), where economic stability influences purchasing behavior. (Testa et al., 2020) indicate that while these consumers are increasingly aware of sustainability issues, they often prioritize cost-effectiveness, reflecting the cultural context of their economic environment. (Garcia-Torres et al., 2019) further emphasize that despite an interest in sustainable fashion, Southern Europeans frequently opt for affordable sustainable options. Understanding these cultural dimensions is crucial for international businesses aiming to effectively engage diverse consumer segments.

The responses to these questions reveal how cultural norms significantly impact consumer behavior regarding sustainable textile products. In collectivist societies, like Japan, societal support for sustainable practices fosters a sense of communal responsibility, aligning with Hofstede's dimension of collectivism. Participants often express pride in contributing to eco-friendly initiatives as a reflection of cultural heritage (Tamura, 2018). In contrast, individualistic cultures, such as the United States, exhibit a growing awareness of sustainability, but societal norms may not be as deeply entrenched. De Mooij (2011) highlights that businesses must tailor their strategies to resonate with these cultural nuances, ensuring sustainable products align with local values and traditions.

The research objective, which sought to determine the specific sustainable initiatives consumers’ desire from textile companies, was addressed through participants' preferences for initiatives such as water reduction, renewable energy adoption, transparency reports, recycling programs, and fair wages. This demonstrates a clear demand for proactive environmental and social responsibility efforts from international industry stakeholders. For example, European participants highlighted the importance of recycling programs and renewable energy, reflecting a broader cultural

commitment to sustainability and environmental responsibility that is often seen in EU policies. This aligns with findings by (Gressgård, 2015), who notes that European consumers tend to prioritize environmental responsibility, influenced by stringent EU regulations and a well-established culture of sustainability. The European Union's commitment to renewable energy and waste management policies further supports this trend, highlighting how cultural and policy frameworks shape consumer preferences in these regions (European Commission, 2020). In contrast, participants from African cultures while valuing sustainability showed a stronger preference for initiatives that directly impact local communities as fair wages and transparency in supply chains, indicating a cultural focus on social equity and community development. This reflects a cultural focus on social equity and community development, as noted by (Blowfield and Frynas, 2005), who discuss how African consumers often prioritize corporate social responsibility initiatives that have tangible benefits for local communities, in terms of fair labor practices and equitable economic development. This is supported by (Amaeshi et al., 2006), who emphasize the importance of community-centred CSR practices in African countries where social responsibility is intertwined with local development goals.

The analysis and results of this study support the main hypotheses generated from the literature review, particularly the identification of environmental irresponsibility, ethical issues, and lack of transparency as priority concerns for consumers. The study also highlights how cultural factors, including the desire to save money, environmental consciousness, and the value of cultural traditions, significantly impact consumer perceptions of recycled clothing. For example, consumers from cultures that value heritage, like those in Latin America, expressed a preference for recycled garments that carry sentimental value, associating them with family traditions and continuity. From the analysis and result of this study, it can be concluded that the main hypotheses generated out of the literature review section of this research are well supported. To begin with, as theory and the analysis of the participants' responses highlighted the identification of environmental irresponsibility, ethical issues, and lack of transparency during the choice of sustainable fashion products is a priority for consumers ("Home Textiles Business Update," 2021). Focusing on the second hypothesis, culture that comprises the desire to save money, being environmentally conscious and valuing cultural traditions to a certain degree has a major effect on consumers' perceptions of buying recycled clothing and other sustainable fashion products as the theoretical framework predicts (Abbate et al., 2024). The participants' exposed preferences in this

study support the literature's statement that the consumers want specific sustainable efforts from textile companies in terms of water usage reduction and renewable energy (Muthu, 2020). Besides supporting the hypotheses formulated based on previous studies, these results contribute to an expanded understanding of the phenomenon in question, establishing the strong evidence of the investigated relationships across the diverse consumers and authenticating the significance of cultural and environmental factors regarding sustainable fashion consumption.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

This research aimed to explore consumer attitudes towards recycled clothing across diverse cultural backgrounds, focusing on how cultural values influence sustainable fashion choices. Conducted through qualitative methodology, the study involved semi-structured interviews with 50 participants to delve into their concerns preferences for sustainable initiatives from textile companies, cultural impacts on purchasing behaviours, usage patterns of sustainable products, and primary drivers behind purchasing decisions. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the interview data starting with open coding to categorize responses into theme as environmental impact, social responsibility and cultural values. Axial coding refined these categories, revealing connections and overarching themes like the role of tradition in clothing choices and the influence of environmental consciousness on consumer behavior. Selective coding focused on core themes such as the demand for transparency in supply chains and the alignment of sustainable products with personal and cultural values. Results presented consumers' prioritization of sustainability including concerns over environmental impact and ethical labor practices, a strong cultural influence on attitudes towards recycled clothing.

5.1 Delimitations of Research

This research on cross-cultural attitudes towards sustainable textiles in the UK is delimited by several factors that shape its scope. The geographical focus exclusively on the UK limits the generalizability of findings to other regions with different cultural point of view and consumer attitudes. The sample size of 50 participants, while diverse in cultural backgrounds did not fully represent all demographic groups within the UK. The study's concentration on consumer perspectives excludes detail from industry stakeholders and policymakers, narrowing the understanding of broader systemic influences on sustainable fashion adoption. Methodologically the use of qualitative methods like semi-structured interviews give a rich subjective insight. Temporal constraints acknowledge that consumer attitudes towards sustainability can evolve over time influenced by changing socio-economic conditions and cultural dynamics.

5.2 Practical Implications

International Textile Companies and other brands understanding the diverse concerns and priorities of consumers highlighted in this study as environmental effect, ethical production and transparency can guide product development and marketing strategies. Companies can use consumer preferences for sustainable materials and practices by investing in renewable energy, reducing water usage, and obtaining certifications that ethical and environmental commitments. Enhancing transparency in supply chains and communicating these efforts to consumers can build trust and loyalty among sustainability-conscious shoppers. For policymakers and regulatory bodies, the study presents the importance of supporting initiatives that promote cross-cultural sustainable fashion practices. Policies that incentivize sustainable production methods, encourage eco-labelling, and enforce fair labor practices can create a conducive environment for international businesses to adopt more sustainable practices. Educating cross-cultural consumers about the environmental and social impacts of their purchasing decisions through public campaigns and educational programs can also foster a more informed consumer base. For all consumers, the research presents the significance of cultural values and norms in shaping attitudes towards

sustainable fashion. Encouraging cross-cultural consumers to align their purchasing behaviors with their cultural values of environmental stewardship and social responsibility can promote more conscientious consumption through providing easily accessible information and resources on sustainable fashion options and their benefits.

5.3 Recommendations for Future Research

Expanding the geographical scope beyond the UK to include diverse cultural contexts globally would enhance the generalizability of findings and provide comparative insights into cross-cultural variations in sustainable fashion adoption. Longitudinal studies could track changes in consumer attitudes and behaviours over time, offering insights into evolving trends and the impact of socio-economic factors on sustainability preferences (Muthu, 2020). Incorporating quantitative methods as qualitative approaches would allow for statistical validation of findings, providing a complete understanding of consumer preferences and behaviours. Exploring the perspectives of industry stakeholders, policymakers, and retailers would shed light on systemic barriers and opportunities for promoting sustainable practices within the textile industry (Ahmed, 1996). Investigating the effectiveness of different communication strategies and interventions aimed at promoting sustainable fashion choices among diverse consumer groups provide practical details for fostering behaviour change towards more sustainable consumption patterns.

References

- Abbate, S., Centobelli, P., Cerchione, R., Nadeem, S. P., & Riccio, E. (2024). Sustainability trends and gaps in the textile, apparel and fashion industries. In *Environment, Development and Sustainability* (Vol. 26, Issue 2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02887-2>
- Ahmad, H., Yaqub, M., & Lee, S. H. (2024). Environmental-, social-, and governance-related factors for business investment and sustainability: a scientometric review of global trends. In *Environment, Development and Sustainability* (Vol. 26, Issue 2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-023-02921-x>
- AlAli, et al. (2019). The Impact of Dividend Policy on Kuwaiti Insurance Companies Share Prices. *World Journal of Finance and Investment Research*, 4(1).
- Al-Hiyari, A., Mas'ud, A., & Kolsi, M. C. (2023). Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Activity and Corporate Controversies in South Africa: The Interacting Role of a Skillful Board. In *Studies in Systems, Decision and Control* (Vol. 216). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-10212-7_29
- Ali Naqvi, P. A., Sulaiman Bagaba, A. S., & Ramzani, S. R. (2018). The consumer price index as a measure of consumer price inflation. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8(2S).
- Audretsch, D. B., Belitski, M., & Korosteleva, J. (2021). Cultural diversity and knowledge in explaining entrepreneurship in European cities. *Small Business Economics*, 56(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00191-4>
- Abbate, S., Centobelli, P., Cerchione, R., Nadeem, S.P., Riccio, E., 2024. Sustainability trends and gaps in the textile, apparel and fashion industries. *Environ Dev Sustain*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02887-2>
- Ahmed, M.I., 1996. Challenges and role of Pakistan textile industry. *Pakistan Textile Journal* 45.

- Ajzen, I. and Driver, B.L., 1991. Prediction of leisure participation from behavioral, normative, and control beliefs: An application of the theory of planned behavior. *Leisure sciences*, 13(3), pp.185-204.
- Alserhan, B.A., 2010. On Islamic branding: Brands as good deeds. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 1(2), pp.101-106.
- Amaeshi, K.M., Adi, B.C., Ogbechie, C. and Amao, O.O., 2006. Corporate social responsibility in Nigeria: Western mimicry or indigenous influences?. *Journal of Corporate Citizenship*, (24), pp.83-99.
- Arnould, E., Crockett, D. and Eckhardt, G., 2021. Informing marketing theory through consumer culture theoretics. *AMS Review*, 11(1), pp.1-8.
- Baraldi, E., Nadin, G., 2006. The challenges in digitalising business relationships. The construction of an IT infrastructure for a textile-related business network. *Technovation* 26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2005.09.016>
- Blowfield, M. and Frynas, J.G., 2005. Setting new agendas: Critical perspectives on corporate social responsibility in the developing world. *International Affairs*, 81(3), pp.499-513.
- Brislin, R. W., & Kim, E. S. (2003). Cultural diversity in people's understanding and uses of time. In *Applied Psychology* (Vol. 52, Issue 3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/1464-0597.00140>
- Chen, P. K., Fortuny-Santos, J., Lujan, I., & Ruiz-de-Arbulo-López, P. (2019). Sustainable manufacturing: Exploring antecedents and influence of Total Productive Maintenance and lean manufacturing. *Advances in Mechanical Engineering*, 11(11). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1687814019889736>
- Carrigan, M. and Attalla, A., 2001. The myth of the ethical consumer – do ethics matter in purchase behaviour? *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 18(7), pp.560-578.
- Chan, R.Y., 2001. Determinants of Chinese consumers' green purchase behavior. *Psychology & Marketing*, 18(4), pp.389-413.

- Chang, H.J., Watchravesringkan, K.T., (2018), 'Who are Sustainably Minded Apparel Shoppers? An Investigation to the Influencing Factors of Sustainable Apparel Consumption'. *International Journal of Retail*, 46 (2), pp.148–162. doi:10.1108/IJRDM- 10- 2016- 0176.
- Chen, H.L. and Burns, L.D., 2006. Environmental analysis of textile products. *Clothing and textiles research journal*, 24(3), pp.248-261.
- Conjoint Analysis Approach', *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, Volume 29, pp. 657-671, ISSN
- Connell, K. Y. H. (2010). Internal and external barriers to eco-conscious apparel acquisition. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 34(3), pp. 279-286.
- Creswell, J. (2020) *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach*. Los Angeles: SAGE.
- Darley, W.K., Luethge, D.J. and Blankson, C., 2013. Culture and international marketing: A sub-Saharan African context. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 26(4), pp.188-202.
- Davies, I.A. and Crane, A., 2003. Ethical decision making in fair trade companies. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 45(1-2), pp.79-92.
- De Mooij, M. and Hofstede, G., 2010. The Hofstede model: Applications to global branding and advertising strategy and research. *International Journal of advertising*, 29(1), pp.85-110.
- De Mooij, M. (2011). *Consumer Behavior and Culture: Consequences for Global Marketing and Advertising*. 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks CA: SAGE Publications, p.49.
- Desore, A., Narula, S.A.(2018), An overview on corporate response towards sustainability issues in textile industry. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 20, pp.1439–1459. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668017-9949-1>
- D'Souza, C., Taghian, M., & Lamb, P. (2006). An empirical study on the influence of environmental labels on consumers. **Corporate Communications: An International Journal**.

- Dheer, R. J. S. (2024). Cultural diversity: an impetus to economic growth—under what conditions? *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 36(7–8). <https://doi.org/10.1080/08985626.2023.2287147>
- Dong, K., & Liu, Y. (2010). Cross-cultural management in China. *Cross Cultural Management: An International Journal*, 17(3). <https://doi.org/10.1108/13527601011068333>
- Dudovskiy, J. (2024). Interpretivism (Interpretivist) Research Philosophy. *Research Methodology*.
- Es Morales, M. P. and Menor, L. S. (2016). An empirical study of Consumers attitude towards sustainable products. *International Journal of Research in Marketing Management*, vol. 4, issue 1.
- European Commission, 2020. A European Green Deal. [online] Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en
- Evidence from a study on Italian consumers. **Business Strategy and the Environment**, 24(4), 252-265.
- Evan, T., & Holý, V. (2023). Cultural diversity and its impact on governance. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seps.2023.101681>
- Flintoft, L. (2009). Taking a position on regulatory diversity. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 10(4). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg2568>
- Funk, A., Sütterlin, B., & Siegrist, M. (2021). Consumer segmentation based on Stated environmentally-friendly behavior in the food domain. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2020.08.010>
- Garcia-Torres, S., Albareda, L., Rey-Garcia, M. and Seuring, S., 2019. Traceability for sustainability—literature review and conceptual framework. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 24(1), pp.85-106.

- Gleim, M.R., Smith, J.S., Andrews, D. and Cronin Jr, J.J., 2013. Against the green: A multi-method examination of the barriers to green consumption. *Journal of retailing*, 89(1), pp.44-61.
- Gressgård, L.J., 2015. Organisational culture, environmental sustainability, and public sector innovation: Cases of innovative public sector organisations. *International Journal of Innovation and Sustainable Development*, 9(3-4), pp.290-305.
- Gupta, S., & Ogden, D. T. (2009). To buy or not to buy? A social dilemma perspective on green buying. **Journal of Consumer Marketing**.
- Gelfand, M. J., Erez, M., & Aycan, Z. (2007). Cross-cultural organizational behavior. In *Annual Review of Psychology* (Vol. 58). <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.58.110405.085559>
- Grimsley, S. (2021). Hofstede's Power Distance: Definition & Examples - Video & Lesson Transcript | Study.com. Study.Com.
- Gul, R. F., Liu, D., Jamil, K., Kamran, M. M., Awan, F. H., & Qaiser, A. (2021). Consumers' assessment of the brand equity of garment brands. *Industria Textila*, 72(6). <https://doi.org/10.35530/IT.072.06.18272>
- Home textiles business update. (2021). *Textile Outlook International*, 2021(209).
- Harris, F., Roby, H. and Dibb, S., (2016), 'Sustainable Clothing: Challenges, Barriers and Interventions for Encouraging More Sustainable Consumer Behaviour'. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 40(3), PP.309-318. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12257>
- Hofstede, G., 1980. Culture and organizations. *International studies of management & organization*, 10(4), pp.15-41.
- Hofstede, G. (2001). **Culture's Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviors, Institutions, and Organizations Across Nations**. Sage Publications.
- Hofstede, G., 2011. Dimensionalizing cultures: The Hofstede model in context. *Online readings in psychology and culture*, 2(1), p.8.

- Hofstede, G. and Minkov, M., (2010). *Cultures and organizations: software of the mind: intercultural cooperation and its importance for survival*. 3rd ed. New York [etc.]: McGraw-Hill.
- Horne, R. E. (2009). Limits to labels: The role of eco-labels in the assessment of product sustainability and routes to sustainable consumption. **International Journal of Consumer Studies**, 33(2), 175-182.
- Hu, S., Henninger, C.E., Boardman, R. and Ryding, D., 2019. Challenging current fashion business models: entrepreneurship through access-based consumption in the second-hand luxury garment sector within a circular economy. *Sustainable luxury: Cases on circular economy and entrepreneurship*, pp.39-54.
- Irshaidat, R. (2022). Interpretivism vs. Positivism in Political Marketing Research. *Journal of Political Marketing*, 21(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/15377857.2019.1624286>
- Irshaidat, R., 2022. Interpretivism vs. Positivism in Political Marketing Research. *Journal of Political Marketing* 21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15377857.2019.1624286>
- Joshi, Y. and Rahman, Z., 2015. Factors affecting green purchase behaviour and future research directions. *International Strategic management review*, 3(1-2), pp.128-143.
- Junjie, M., Yingxin, M., 2022. The Discussions of Positivism and Interpretivism. *Global Academic Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 4. <https://doi.org/10.36348/gajhss.2022.v04i01.002>
- Jayashree, G., & Priya, C. (2019). Design of visibility for order lifecycle using datawarehouse. *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, 8(6). <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijeat.F9171.088619>
- Kanz, O., Brüggemann, F., Ding, K., Bittkau, K., Rau, U., & Reinders, A. (2023). Life-cycle global warming impact of hydrogen transport through pipelines from Africa to Germany. *Sustainable Energy and Fuels*, 7(13). <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3se00281k>
- Khelif, H. (2016). Hofstede's cultural dimensions in accounting research: A review. In *Meditari Accountancy Research* (Vol. 24, Issue 4). <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-02-2016-0041>

- Krugman, P., Obstfeld, M., & Melitz, M. (2018). *International Economics: Theory and Policy, Global Edition*. In *International Economics: Theory and Policy, Global Edition*.
- Kim, Y. and Choi, S.M., 2005. Antecedents of green purchase behavior: An examination of collectivism, environmental concern, and PCE. *Advances in consumer research*, 32, p.592.
- Koirala, S., 2019. SMEs: Key drivers of green and inclusive growth.
- Kozłowski, A., Searcy, C. and Bardecki, M., 2015. Corporate sustainability reporting in the apparel industry: An analysis of indicators disclosed. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 64(3), pp.377-397.
- Kumar, P., & Noble, C. H. (2016). Beyond form and function: Why do consumers value product design? *Journal of Business Research*, 69(2), 613-620.
- Laroche, M., Bergeron, J. and Barbaro-Forleo, G., 2001. Targeting consumers who are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products. *Journal of consumer marketing*, 18(6), pp.503-520.
- Leavy, P. ed., 2014. *The Oxford handbook of qualitative research*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Lee, K., 2014. Predictors of sustainable consumption among young educated consumers in Hong Kong. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 26(3), pp.217-238.
- León-Mantero, C., Casas-Rosal, J.C., Pedrosa-Jesús, C., Maz-Machado, A., 2020. Measuring attitude towards mathematics using Likert scale surveys: The weighted average. *PLoS One* 15. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239626>
- Lochmiller, C.R., 2021. Conducting thematic analysis with qualitative data. *Qualitative Report* 26. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2021.5008>
- Loo, T. and Davies, G., 2006. Branding China: The ultimate challenge in reputation management? *Corporate reputation review*, 9, pp.198-210.
- Lee, C. S., & Park, H. H. (2017). Structural aspects of transglutaminase 2: functional, structural, and regulatory diversity. In *Apoptosis* (Vol. 22, Issue 9). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10495-017-1396-9>

- Lee, Y.-T., & Gyamfi, N. Y. A. (2022). The Sage handbook of contemporary cross-cultural management. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 53(3). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41267-021-00443-0>
- Lifintsev, D., & Wellbrock, W. (2019). Cross-cultural communication in the digital age. *Estudos Em Comunicacao*, 1(28). <https://doi.org/10.25768/fal.ec.n28.a05>
- Lochmiller, C. R. (2021). Conducting thematic analysis with qualitative data. *Qualitative Report*, 26(6). <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2021.5008>
- Lombardi Netto, A., Salomon, V. A. P., Ortiz-Barrios, M. A., Florek-Paszowska, A. K., Petrillo, A., & De Oliveira, O. J. (2021). Multiple criteria assessment of sustainability programs in the textile industry. *International Transactions in Operational Research*, 28(3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/itor.12871>
- Luna, D., & Gupta, S. F. (2001). An integrative framework for cross-cultural consumer behavior. *International Marketing Review*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1108/02651330110381998>
- Marais, F., Van der Lugt, C. T., & Mans-Kemp, N. (2022). Mainstreaming environmental, social and governance integration in investment practices in South Africa: A proposed framework. *Journal of Economic and Financial Sciences*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.4102/jef.v15i1.787>
- Marquesone, R. de F. P., & Carvalho, T. C. M. de B. (2022). Examining the Nexus between the Vs of Big Data and the Sustainable Challenges in the Textile Industry. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084638>
- Magnusson, M.K., Arvola, A., Hursti, U.K.K., Åberg, L. and Sjöden, P.O., 2003. Choice of organic foods is related to perceived consequences for human health and to environmentally friendly behaviour. *Appetite*, 40(2), pp.109-117.
- McNeill, L. and Moore, R., 2015. Sustainable fashion consumption and the fast fashion conundrum: fashionable consumers and attitudes to sustainability in clothing choice. *International journal of consumer studies*, 39(3), pp.212-222.
- Minton, E.A., Spielmann, N., Kahle, L.R., and Kim, C.H., 2018. The subjective norms of sustainable consumption: A cross-cultural exploration. *Journal of Business Research*, 82, pp. 400-408.

- Mukendi, A., Davies, I., Glozer, S. and McDonagh, P., 2020. Sustainable fashion: current and future research directions. *European journal of marketing*, 54(11), pp.2873-2909.
- Muthu, S.S., 2020. *Assessing the environmental impact of textiles and the clothing supply chain*. Woodhead publishing.
- Niinimäki, K. (2010). Eco-clothing, consumer identity and ideology. **Sustainable Development**, 18(3), 150-162.
- Orr, G., 2003. Diffusion of innovations, by Everett Rogers (1995). Retrieved January, 21, p.2005.
- Priya, Berry, S. and Agrawal, P.R., 2024. Sustainable Textile Production in the Developing Countries: Major Challenges or Concerns and Their Possible Solutions. In *Dye Pollution from Textile Industry: Challenges and Opportunities for Sustainable Development* (pp. 263-278). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Patton, M.Q., 1987. How to use qualitative methods in evaluation (No. 4). Sage.
- Palak Gupta, & Dubey, A. (2016). E-commerce-study of privacy, trust and security from consumer's perspective. *International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing*, 5(6).
- Panina, D., & Kroumova, M. (2015). Cross-Cultural Communication Patterns In Computer Mediated Communication. *Journal of International Education Research (JIER)*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.19030/jier.v11i1.9092>
- Ponomareva, Y., Uman, T., Bodolica, V., & Wennberg, K. (2022). Cultural diversity in top management teams: Review and agenda for future research. In *Journal of World Business* (Vol. 57, Issue 4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2022.101328>
- Raithel, K., van Knippenberg, D., & Stam, D. (2021). Team Leadership and Team Cultural Diversity: The Moderating Effects of Leader Cultural Background and Leader Team Tenure. *Journal of Leadership and Organizational Studies*, 28(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/15480518211010763>

- Richards, S. E., Wijeweera, C., & Wijeweera, A. (2022). Lifestyle and socioeconomic determinants of diabetes: Evidence from country-level data. *PLoS ONE*, 17(7 July). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0270476>
- Richieri Hanania, L. (2016). The UNESCO Convention on the Diversity of Cultural Expressions as a coordination framework to promote regulatory coherence in the creative economy. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 22(4). <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286632.2015.1025068>
- Sahadevan, P., & Sumangala, M. (2021). Effective Cross-Cultural Communication for International Business. *Shanlax International Journal of Management*, 8(4). <https://doi.org/10.34293/management.v8i4.3813>
- Senthilkannan Muthu, S. (2020). Assessing the Environmental Impact of Textiles and the Clothing Supply Chain. In *Assessing the Environmental Impact of Textiles and the Clothing Supply Chain*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2019-0-00463-3>
- Sardana, N., Shekoochi, S., Cornett, E.M., Kaye, A.D., 2023. Qualitative and quantitative research methods, in: *Substance Use and Addiction Research: Methodology, Mechanisms, and Therapeutics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-98814-8.00008-1>
- Schlosser, S., Boedeker, M. and Aribarg, A., 2006. Middle Eastern luxury consumers: Motivation for luxury consumption and the role of status in the global marketplace. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 19(3), pp.37-53.
- Shen, B., 2014. Sustainable fashion supply chain: Lessons from H&M. *Sustainability*, 6(9), pp.6236-6249.
- Soares, A.M., Farhangmehr, M., Shoham, A., 2007. Hofstede's dimensions of culture in international marketing studies. *J Bus Res* 60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2006.10.018>
- Soyer, M., and Dittrich, K., (2021) 'Sustainable Consumer Behavior in Purchasing, Using and Disposing of Clothes'. *Sustainability* 13(15), 8333.
- Spiegel, R. and Meadows, D., 2010. *Green building materials: a guide to product selection and specification*. John Wiley & Sons.

- Statista, 2024. Challenges Faced by Fashion Executives to Improving Consumer Perceptions of Their Company's Sustainability Credentials Worldwide in 2022.
- Stern, P.C., Dietz, T., Abel, T., Guagnano, G.A. and Kalof, L., 1999. A value-belief-norm theory of support for social movements: The case of environmentalism. *Human ecology review*, pp.81-97.
- Tamura, M., 2018. The culture of thrift and environmental sustainability in Japan: Lessons for the West. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(4), pp.1-9.
- Testa, F., Iovino, R. and Iraldo, F., 2020. The circular economy and consumer behaviour: The mediating role of information seeking in buying circular packaging. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(8), pp.3435-3448.
- Thøgersen, J. and Schrader, U., 2012. From knowledge to action—new paths towards sustainable consumption. *Journal of Consumer Policy*, 35, pp.1-5.
- Todeschini, B.V., Cortimiglia, M.N., Callegaro-de-Menezes, D. and Ghezzi, A., 2017. Innovative and sustainable business models in the fashion industry: Entrepreneurial drivers, opportunities, and challenges. *Business horizons*, 60(6), pp.759-770.
- Triandis, H.C., 1995. A theoretical framework for the study of diversity.
- Vaismoradi, M., Jones, J., Turunen, H. and Snelgrove, S., 2016. Theme development in qualitative content analysis and thematic analysis.
- Vermeir, I. and Verbeke, W., 2006. Sustainable food consumption: Exploring the consumer “attitude– behavioral intention” gap. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental ethics*, 19, pp.169-194.
- Wang, L., Xu, Y., Lee, H., Li, A., (2022) 'Preferred Product Attributes for Sustainable Outdoor Apparel: A
- Weyant, E., 2022. Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches, 5th Edition. *Journal of Electronic Resources in Medical Libraries* 19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15424065.2022.2046231>

- Weyant, E. (2022). Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches, 5th Edition. *Journal of Electronic Resources in Medical Libraries*, 19(1–2).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15424065.2022.2046231>
- Whitaker, A. (2021). Price Elasticity of Demand. In *Economics of Visual Art*.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108649919.019>
- Yarrow, K. and O'Donnell, J., 2009. *Gen buy: How tweens, teens and twenty-somethings are revolutionizing retail*. John Wiley and Sons.
- Zhang, X., Ding, X., Ma, L., & Wang, G. (2018). Identifying factors preventing sustainable brand loyalty among consumers: A mixed methods approach. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(12).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su10124685>

Appendices

Appendix 1

Ethical Forms

Module Code (Legacy):	
Module Code:	BUSI1710
Tutor Name:	Xinrui Liu
Project Title:	The cross-cultural consumers' attitude towards sustainability of product in the Textile Industry
Group members:	
Brief description of project objectives and methods:	This study presents four different research objectives: 1. Explore how the complexity of sustainable product features may deter cross-cultural consumers from understanding their benefits and engaging with them effectively. 2. Evaluate the variations in cross-cultural consumer preferences for specific sustainable product features and their impact on engagement with the sustainable textile industry. 3. Assess whether consumers' willingness to pay for sustainable products varies across different demographic groups and income levels, potentially affecting the perceived importance of price. 4. To provide recommendations for textile industry on prioritizing affordable sustainable product features to enhance cross-cultural consumer engagement and promote wider adoption. This research project will use a qualitative analysis research methodology to investigate the impact of sustainable product features on cross-cultural consumer engagement. Qualitative analysis will offer deep and comprehensive insights into cross-cultural consumers' sustainable product adaptation by revealing their experiences, opinions, and challenges (Patton, 1987). The methodology, which covers data collection, sampling strategy, data analysis, and ethics.
Start of data collection:	24 May 2024
End of data collection:	10 August 2024
Data collection methods (select all that apply):	In person interview/focus group
For data collection involving human participants:	
I will use the required Participant Information and Consent templates:	Yes
I will not collect data from University staff, children or vulnerable people:	Yes
I will collect only the minimum personal data necessary to answer my research questions:	Yes
Any in-person contact with participants will only occur in quiet public spaces:	Yes
I will not collect the identities of people who respond to questionnaires (anonymity):	Yes
I will not include or report the names of individuals alongside data I store about them (confidentiality):	Yes
For all data collected:	
I will store data only on my University G: drive or University OneDrive and not on mobile devices, memory sticks or laptops:	Yes
I will delete all collected data at the end of this academic year:	Yes
Explain reasons for any NAs above	

Appendix 2

Personal Information

Can you please introduce yourself? (Name, Age, Gender, Occupation, Nationality)

How would you describe your cultural background?

Sr. No.	Theme	Question Statement
1	Concern	What are your main concerns or priorities when it comes to sustainable textile products?
2		What sustainable initiatives would you like to see more from textile companies?
3	Purchasing Factors	What factors do you consider most important when buying textile products (e.g., price, quality, environmental impact, social responsibility)? Rate the factors and their importance
4		Are there any specific sustainable textile brands or products that you prefer, and why?
5	Cultural Influence	How do you think your cultural background and values influence your attitudes towards recycled cloths? Provide example
6	Usage Pattern	How often do you purchase sustainable products like organic cotton shirts or recycled polyester jackets?
7	Purchase Drivers	What is your main reason for buying eco-friendly products like organic cotton shirts or recycled polyester jackets? (e.g., environmental concern, quality)
		Do you feel that community and societal norms in your culture support the purchase of sustainable textile products?
		How important is it for you that sustainable products align with your cultural traditions and values?

Appendix 3

Interview Responses

Sr. No.	Theme	Question Statement	Responses
1	Concern	What are your main concerns or priorities when it comes to sustainable textile products?	Participants across various regions, including North America (NA/CA), Europe (EU/UK), Asia (AS/JP), South America (SA/BR), and Australia (AU/AU), expressed a focus on environmental impact, labor conditions, transparency, durability, affordability, organic materials, product lifecycle, certifications, social impact, and energy consumption.
2	Concern	What sustainable initiatives would you like to see more from textile companies?	Respondents from North America (NA/US), Europe (EU/FR), Asia (AS/CN), South America (SA/AR), and Africa (AF/ZA) indicated a preference for initiatives such as water reduction, renewable energy, transparency reports, recycling programs, the use of organic materials, fair wages, environmental collaborations, certifications, educational campaigns, and improved product durability.
3	Purchasing Factors	What factors do you consider most important when buying textile products (e.g., price, quality, environmental impact, social responsibility)? Rate the factors and their importance	Respondents from North America (NA/CA and NA/US), Europe (EU/UK, EU/DE, and EU/FR), and Asia (AS/IN) rated price, affordability, environmental impact, sustainable materials, low carbon footprint, social responsibility, ethical production, and fair trade as crucial factors.
4	Purchasing Factors	Are there any specific sustainable textile brands or products that you prefer, and why?	Participants from Asia (AS/JP and AS/CN), South America (SA/BR and SA/AR), Australia (AU/AU), and Africa (AF/ZA) favored brands known for transparency, the use of organic materials, commitment to sustainability, fair labor practices, and lifecycle analysis.

5	Cultural Influence	How do you think your cultural background and values influence your attitudes towards recycled clothes? Provide examples	Individuals from North America (NA/CA), Europe (EU/FR), Asia (AS/JP), South America (SA/BR), and Australia (AU/AU) mentioned that their cultural background influences their attitudes towards recycled clothes through values of sustainability, thriftiness, heritage, environmental stewardship, and sentimentality.
6	Usage Pattern	How often do you purchase sustainable products like organic cotton shirts or recycled polyester jackets?	Consumers from North America (NA/US), Europe (EU/DE), Asia (AS/CN), South America (SA/BR), Australia (AU/AU), and Africa (AF/ZA) reported varying purchase frequencies, with some buying organic cotton shirts or recycled polyester jackets frequently, while others do so seasonally based on weather needs.
7	Purchase Drivers	What is your main reason for buying eco-friendly products like organic cotton shirts or recycled polyester jackets?	Respondents from North America (NA/US), Europe (EU/DE), Asia (AS/CN), South America (SA/BR), and Australia (AU/AU) highlighted environmental concerns, quality, personal values, cost-effectiveness, ethical considerations, and product attributes as primary reasons for their purchases.
8	Cultural Influence	Do you feel that community and societal norms in your culture support the purchase of sustainable textile products?	Participants from Europe (EU/DE), Asia (AS/JP), North America (NA/US), and Africa (AF/ZA) observed that community and societal norms generally support the purchase of sustainable textile products.
9	Cultural Alignment	How important is it for you that sustainable products align with your cultural traditions and values?	Respondents from Asia (AS/CN), South America (SA/BR), Europe (EU/FR), and Africa (AF/ZA) emphasized the importance of aligning sustainable products with their cultural traditions and values.

Appendix 4

Consent Form

Hello, my name is Suma and I am a student pursuing a degree in International Business at the University of Greenwich. I am currently conducting a research project titled "The Cross-Cultural Consumers' Attitudes towards Sustainability of Products in the Textile Industry."

Your insights and experiences will be invaluable in understanding how cultural differences influence consumer attitudes towards sustainability in the textile industry across various regions.

Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. By proceeding with this interview, you consent to the use of your responses for the purposes of this research. Your responses will be kept confidential, and your identity will remain anonymous.

Thank you for your time and contribution.

By signing below, you acknowledge that you have read and understood the consent statement and agree to participate in this study.

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Basic Information Sheet

1. **Would you like to state the name of your organization? (Optional)**

Name of Organization: _____

2. **What is your current role within the organization? (Optional)**

Current Role: _____

3. **Can you briefly describe your primary responsibilities in your current role? (Optional)**

Primary Responsibilities: _____

4. **How many years of experience do you have in the textile industry? (Optional)**

Years of Experience: _____

Interview Questions

1. Concern

- What are your main concerns or priorities when it comes to sustainable textile products?

Answer: _____

- What sustainable initiatives would you like to see more from textile companies?

Answer: _____

2. Purchasing Factors

- What factors do you consider most important when buying textile products (e.g., price, quality, environmental impact, social responsibility)? Please rate the factors and their importance.

Answer: _____

- Are there any specific sustainable textile brands or products that you prefer, and why?

Answer: _____

3. Cultural Influence

- How do you think your cultural background and values influence your attitudes towards recycled clothes? Please provide examples.

Answer: _____

4. Usage Pattern

- How often do you purchase sustainable products like organic cotton shirts or recycled polyester jackets?

Answer: _____

5. Purchase Drivers

- What is your main reason for buying eco-friendly products like organic cotton shirts or recycled polyester jackets?

Answer: _____

- Do you feel that community and societal norms in your culture support the purchase of sustainable textile products?

Answer: _____

- How important is it for you that sustainable products align with your cultural traditions and values?

Answer: _____

